

THE INFLUENCE OF MOTHER TONGUE TOWARDS LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS OF SULU NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The study is a descriptive research which deals with the influence of mother tongue towards learning English language among senior high school students of Sulu National High School..It also discusses the respondents' socio-demographic characteristics, including gender, age, ethnicity, grade level, and parents' educational background, as well as the degree to which mother tongue influences Sulu National High School senior high school students. It also addresses the notable variations in the degree to which mother tongue influences English language acquisition among Sulu National High School senior high school students at MBHTE - Division of Sulu when data are categorized by socio-demographic profile, including gender, age, strand, grade level, and parental educational attainment. Purposive sampling procedure was used in selecting the respondents of the study. The research instrument is composed of two parts. Part I is about the demographic profile of the respondents which includes their gender, age, strand, and grade level, and parent's educational attainment. Part II is composed of 20 statements on the influence of mother tongue in English language learning among senior high school students of Sulu National High School. There are five (5) options available, ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." It was discovered that the parents are not highly educated, the senior high school children of the appropriate age for their current grade level, and an equal number were selected from each strand. All of the respondents concur that learning English depends in part on one's mother tongue. Regarding gender, age, grade level, strand, and parents' educational attainment, there is no discernible difference.

Keywords: *Mother tongue, English language learning, SNHS, Senior High School, Descriptive research.*

INTRODUCTION

A child learns their mother tongue as their first language, according to Ojo (2005). In their formative years. Mother tongues are not taught; they are learnt. The children's early ideas are encoded in their mother tongue. The mother tongue of a multilingual person acts as a symbol of their original culture. Mother language also contributes to the preservation of cultural heritage and practices. It is a source of pride and a sense of belonging that is integral to peoples' identities. Because of this, it's imperative to cherish mother tongue and promote its use and learning.

The best language abilities and intuitive understanding are found in mother tongues. It facilitates successful communication for the multilingual individual. The student must possess the fundamental abilities of speaking, reading, writing, and listening. A person's mother tongue is necessary for their sociolinguistic, cultural, and personal uniqueness. When speaking and acting in one's mother tongue, one reflects societal norms. A group of people's mother tongue eventually turns into their primary means of cognition and communication, Benson (2005).

A person's mother tongue is responsible for identifying their level of language proficiency. When learning one's mother tongue, both conscious and unconscious approaches are employed. A child learns their mother tongue consciously through listening. The mother tongue plays a crucial role in the growth of education's intellectual, moral, and academic domains. Speaking in one's native tongue facilitates comprehension, handling, and communication in all other academic topics. Someone may be able to communicate and think coherently if they are fluent in their mother tongue. It will be difficult for students whose mother tongue is weak to express themselves or their thoughts. A person cannot have fresh insights, appreciation, extension, or expansion of notions unless they are able to understand the subject matter through their mother tongue (Awopetu, 2016).

The findings of Boga's (2015) study, which was carried out in Davao City, show that students' native tongue language effect makes it difficult for them to understand other courses offered in English. Using one's native tongue as a teaching medium has benefits, but it also affects students' English language proficiency, which could cause issues academically by the time they reach fourth grade, according to one English teacher in the Province of Davao del Sur, specifically in Digos City, Bancalé (2018).

Lina Septianasari (2019) embarks the study about the “problems with mother tongue and difficulties learning English as a foreign language”. For some learners, learning English as a foreign language (EFL) can be quite difficult. Somehow, learning their mother tongue can be a barrier to understanding the new language. The interference

of their mother tongue has a somewhat negative impact on EFL learners' language acquisition. Finding out how learners' mother tongues affect their English language competency and what difficulties EFL learners encounter when learning English as a second language are the two main objectives of this study. This sample's population consists of EFL students at Bandung University. To get the data, the researcher employed purposive sampling. When gathering data, triangulation is employed. These are the interview, test items, and observation. The data is analyzed using applicable theories. The data illustrates how phonological and grammatical characteristics of a learner's native language impact their ability to produce language. Speech production is difficult for English as a foreign language (EFL) speakers because English and Bahasa Indonesia have distinct sound systems. Mother tongue interference has been found to impact English vowels and consonants.

Drs. Judie Arulappan and Davis Daniel started studying the "influence of mother tongue in teaching and learning English language" in 2020. Language is the random creation of symbols that convey ideas, information, emotions, and wants. Thoughts, ideas, and feelings are connected through language. One tool for communication is language. People utilize many different languages all throughout the world. Despite the fact that all languages are intended for communication, a lot of individuals communicate in English. People who do not speak English as their mother tongue also utilize it. English language instruction is crucial in the era of globalization. English is the only official language in the world that is universally understood. The effect of mother tongue on English language learning and education has long been a topic of discussion. The dissimilar sound systems of the mother tongue and the English spelling system are the cause of the pronunciation errors. Therefore, the problem can be rectified by including the English language in the core curriculum and promoting spoken English fluency. The sound patterns that are likely to confuse and make you stumble when speaking your mother tongue can be recognized and practiced. Students should practice these sound patterns on a regular basis using a native speaker's model voice. These actions will eliminate the mother tongue's influence on English language education and learning, resulting in a faster rate of English language acquisition.

English language instruction has become increasingly important in Nigeria over time. The Ikom Local Government Area was the subject of a case study conducted by Ochagu, Kaka A., and Agban Joy Obim in 2022 for their study, "Influence of Mother-Tongue on English Language Use Selected Mother-Tongue Factors Affecting English Language Usage." Given the importance of English and its practical applications, English language proficiency is a must for all Nigerians. This is due to the fact that national language development in Nigeria is impossible due to linguistic variation. This explains why English is associated with significant usage domains in Nigeria. The aim of this research was to investigate and gain a deeper understanding of the influence of mother tongue on English spoken in Nigeria. This study focuses on specific mother-tongue elements that influence Nigerians speak English. To properly modify components and yield reliable results, the goal of this work is to examine mother-tongue interference at the phonetic and phonological levels. 150 Ikom learners/users of English, whose mother tongue is Ikom, were selected as SSS3 students from three high schools in the Ikom

Local Government Area of the Cross-River State. Apart from (phonetic) articulation assessments, tape recorders and smart recorders were employed to gather data. For the data analysis, a quantitative and descriptive methodology was used. The internet, newspapers, online and physical libraries, and pertinent textbooks were used as data sources. The findings show that English has a negative impact on the mother tongue of Ikom users and learners when it comes to pronouncing English vowels, consonants, and consonant clusters as well as supra-segmental elements like stress and intonation.

Based on the aforementioned study, this research will ascertain the degree to which mother tongue influences English language acquisition at MBHTE-Sulu in the 2023–2024 school year. The purpose of this study is to collect empirical data that will form the foundation for describing how mother tongue influences English language acquisition.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of influence of mother tongue towards learning English language among senior high school students of Sulu National High School, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education in Sulu during the School Year-2024.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the students-respondents at Sulu National High School, MBHTE-Sulu in terms of:
 - 1.1 Gender;
 - 1.2 Age;
 - 1.3 Grade Level;
 - 1.4 Strand; and
 - 1.5 Parent's Educational Attainment?
2. What is the extent of influence of mother tongue towards learning English language among senior high school students at Sulu National High School, MBHTE-Sulu?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of influence of mother tongue towards learning English language among senior high school students at Sulu National High School when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of:
 - 1.1 Gender;
 - 1.2 Age;
 - 1.3 Grade Level;
 - 1.4 Strand; and
 - 1.5 Parent's Educational Attainment?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-survey research approach to determine how mother tongue influence in learning English language among senior high school students at Sulu National High School. Any potential consequences of implementing the remote learning program will be outlined in the previously mentioned design.

Information about the topic was created using this style. The study aims to characterize and measure how mother tongue affects students' learning of the English language. With this strategy, they were able to make sense of their ambiguity in their field of study.

Research Locale

Numerous senior high school students at Sulu National High School were the subject of this study. This is scheduled to take place at the aforementioned school in 2023–2024. This school is among the populated in the province.

Respondents of the study

Senior high school students from Sulu National High School are involved in this study. The finding out what respondents think about the influence of mother tongue towards learning English language is the aim of the study. The respondents listed above have been categorized based on their areas of academic expertise.

Patikul District, MBHTE-Sulu

Sulu National High School

Grade level	Strand	Section	frequency
Grade 11	Stem	1	10
Grade 11	ABM	2	10
Grade 11	HUMSS	2	10
Grade 11	GAS	2	10
Grade 11	Arts and Design	1	10
Grade 12	Stem	1	10
Grade 12	ABM	2	10
Grade 12	GAS	2	10

Grade 12	Arts and Design	1	10
Grade 12	HUMSS	2	10
Total			100

Sampling Design

The sample method that was employed is the purposive sampling procedure. In order to get information from the respondents, the researcher uses a sampling strategy. The best way to collect participant data is through this approach. The survey questionnaire is then disseminated.

By employing this sampling strategy, the researchers can obtain the data they need for their respondents very rapidly. All they do is provide the selected respondents with the survey questions.

Data Gathering Procedures

In the collection of the data, the following steps will be employed:

- 1) First, permission to administer the questionnaire was obtained from the Sulu State College Graduate Studies Dean; next, the Sulu National High School Principal; and last, the Senior High School Coordinator.
- 2) The researcher launched, administered, and retrieved the questionnaire personally.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire was the instruments in this study in gathering the data on demographic profile and the extent of the influence of mother tongue towards learning English language among senior high school students at Sulu National High School. The purpose of the survey is to gather information on how mother tongue has improved English language proficiency at Sulu National High School, MBHTE-Sulu senior high school students in the academic year 2023–2024. This Survey questionnaire was adapted from the study of Olu Oyewole, Ph.D (2017).

The research instruments employed in this investigation were divided into two components. The first section of the questionnaire asked questions about the respondents' age, gender, grade level, and parents' educational attainment. Additionally, the second section concentrated on gathering information about how much senior high school students at Sulu National High School were influenced by their mother tongue when learning English.

Under the extent of the influence of mother tongue towards learning English language among senior high school students at Sulu National High School contained

twenty (20) items and were answered through 5-points likert scales such as 5=Strongly Agree, 4=Agree, 3=Undecided, 2=Disagree, 1=strongly disagree.

Statistical Treatment of Data

1. For the research problem number one (1), the socio-demographic profile of the respondents at Sulu National High School, MBHTE-Sulu, was ascertained by using frequency and percentage in relation to the following variables: gender, age, grade level, and parental educational attainment.
2. For the research problem number two (2), The study employed means and standard deviation to evaluate the influence of mother tongue on English language learning among senior high school students at Sulu National High School, MBHTE-Sulu as well as the variables that led them to sign up for the program.
3. For research problem number three (3), One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the significant differences when the data were grouped according to age, civil status, Strand, and parents educational attainment; when the data were grouped according to gender, the t-test for independent samples was used to determine the extent of influence of mother tongue towards learning English language among senior high school students at Sulu National High School, MBHTE-Sulu.

RESULTS

1. *What is the socio - demographic profile of the senior high school students of Sulu National High School in terms of 1.1 gender, 1.2 age, 1.3 grade level, and 1.4 parent’s educational attainment?*

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Table 1.1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender. Fifty-three percent (53%) of the respondents are males and 47% are females.

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	53	53%
Female	47	47%
TOTAL	100	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Table 1.2 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age. It showed that 85% of the respondents are between 16 – 20 years old and only 3% are 15 years old and below.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
15 years old and below	3	3%
16 – 20 years old	85	85%
21 – 25 years old	12	12%
TOTAL	100	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Grade Level

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of grade level. It showed that 50% of the respondents were taken from each grade level.

Table 1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 11	50	50%
Grade 12	50	50%
TOTAL	100	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Strand

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of strand. The table shows that almost equal number of respondents were taken from each strand.

Table 1.4 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Strand

Strand	Frequency	Percentage
STEM	21	21%
HUMSS	20	20%
ABM	20	20%
GAS	19	10%
Arts and Design	20	20%
TOTAL	100	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Parent's Educational Attainment

Table 1.5 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of parent's educational attainment. It showed that 45% of the parents reached elementary level in education while only 7% has no formal education. None of the parents finish masters/doctorate degree.

Table 1.4 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
No Formal Education	7	7%
Elementary Level	45	45%
Secondary Level	28	28%
College Level	20	20%
Masters/Doctorate Degree	0	0%
TOTAL	100	100%

2. What is the extent of influence of mother tongue towards learning English language among senior high school students of Sulu National High School, MBHTE – Sulu?

Table 2.1 presents the influence of mother tongue towards learning English language among senior high school students of Sulu National High School.

It showed that the respondents indicated **strongly agree** only in statement 11 and **undecided** in statement 20 only. For the rest of the statements, they indicated **agree**. They **strongly agree** that it is easy for the students to understand the lessons with the use of mother tongue (mean = 4.566, SD = .592) and **undecided** if mother tongue can distract students' confidence (mean = 3.475, SD = .761). For **agree**, some of the statements are; mother tongue can boost students' comprehension about the subject (mean = 4.152, SD = .541); Students who are dependent on their mother tongue may find it difficult to form basic sentences in the English language (Mean = 4.172, SD = .655); and mother tongue can lead to students' difficulties in learning English language (mean = 4.040, SD = .638). The average mean of 3.758 means that the respondents **agree** that mother tongue can influence learning English language among senior high school students of Sulu National High School, MBHTE – Sulu.

Table 2.1 Extent of the Influence of Mother Tongue in Learning English Language among Senior High School Students of Sulu National High School, MBHTE – Sulu

INFLUENCE OF MOTHER TONGUE	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Mother tongue can alter the way students read and speak in English.	3.990	.631	Agree
2. Students can be greatly affected if they use English language to explain some concept in the subject itself and not in their mother tongue.	3.849	.360	Agree
3. Permission to use mother tongue in teaching can affect other language especially in English language.	3.717	.453	Agree
4. Students can adapt to the teaching and learning environment without the use of mother tongue.	3.707	.520	Agree
5. Students always have good grade in a subject that teachers use mother tongue to teach.	3.970	.677	Agree
6. The use of mother tongue in school as way of effective communication can be corrected and student will adapt to it.	3.849	.787	Agree
7. Explanation of subject's concept in mother tongue brings about proper understanding and assimilation.	4.141	.404	Agree
8. The student's use of mother tongue can affect other grammar language.	4.141	.452	Agree

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9. It is necessary for a teacher to use the student's mother tongue for effective communication to take place.	3.929	.520	Agree
10. Students who is addicted to use mother tongue may likely to have problem in constructing simple sentence in English language.	4.172	.655	Agree
11. It is easy for the students to understand the lessons with the use of mother tongue.	4.566	.592	Strongly Agree
12. Mother tongue can boost students' comprehension about the subject.	4.152	.541	Agree
13. Mother tongue is a reflection of what has been instilled in a child from childhood or from his/her school.	3.990	.814	Agree
14. The use of mother tongue in school can enhance students' confidence.	3.788	.558	Agree
15. Students can easily understand the instruction when mother tongue is observed.	3.960	.684	Agree
16. It is necessary for the students to use mother tongue in school.	3.920	.340	Agree
17. Students who is addicted to use of mother tongue may get a higher grade.	3.920	.650	Agree
18. Mother tongue can enhance students' motivation in learning.	3.798	.969	Agree
19. Mother tongue can lead to students' difficulties in learning English language.	4.040	.638	Agree
20. Mother tongue can distract students' confidence.	3.475	.761	Undecided
AVERAGE	3.758		AGREE

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.50 – 4.49	Agree
3	2.50 – 3.49	Undecided
2	1.50 – 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of the influence of mother tongue towards learning English language among senior high school students of sulu National School, MBHTE – Sulu when data are grouped according to age, gender, grade level, strand, and parent’s educational attainment?

The t-test was used for gender since there are only two categories. The sig. value of 0.540 is greater than the p - .05, 2- tailed tests. It means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

There is no significant difference in the extent of the influence of mother tongue in learning English language among senior high school students of Sulu National High School, MBHTE- Sulu when data are grouped according to their gender.

Table 3.1 t – test for Significant Difference in the Extent of the extent of influence of mother tongue towards learning English language among senior high school students at Sulu National High School in terms of Gender

		Mean					
Variables		Mean	SD	Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Extent of the factors affecting interest in learning	Male	4.790	.620	0.540	29.380	.2509	Not Significant
	Female	4.250	.810				

Significant at .05 level

In Table 3.2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used for age, grade level, strand, and parent’s educational attainment.

The sig. value of 0.424 for age is greater than the p - value of .05 and the sig. value of 0.295 for grade level is greater than the p-value at .05, the sig. value of 0.918 for strand is greater than the sig. value of .05, and the sig. value of 0.074 for parent’ educational attainment is also greater than the p - value of .05.

Table 3.2 ANOVA for Significant Difference in the Extent of the Influence of Mother Tongue in English Language Learning among Senior High School Students of Sulu National High School in terms of Age, Grade Level, Parent’s Educational Attainment, and Parent’s Average Monthly Income

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig.	Interpretation
AGE						
Between Group	1.752	3	0.584	0.951	.424	Not Significant
Within Group	58.975	96	0.614			
Total	60.727	99				
Grade Level						
Between Group	.519	1	0.519	1.147	.295	Not Significant
Within Group	44.386	98	0.453			
Total	44.907	99				
Strand						
Between Group	.602	4	0.150	0.237	.918	Not Significant
Within Group	60.125	95	0.633			
Total	60.727	99				
Parent’s Educational Attainment						
Between Group	.175	4	0.044	0.074	.990	Not Significant
Within Group	56.512	95	0.595			
Total	56.687	99				

Significant at .05 level

DISCUSSION

1. On the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender, age, grade level, strand, and parent’s educational attainment

The result showed that more than half of the respondents are males, majority of which are between 16 – 20 years old. Equal number of respondents were taken from grade level and strand. Almost half of the parents were able to attend elementary level only in education.

It implies that senior high school students of Sulu National High School are mostly males in the right age for their present grade level and the parents are not very educated.

2. On the extent of the influence of mother tongue in English language learning among senior high school students of Sulu National High School MBHTE – Sulu

The senior high school students of Sulu National High School **agree** that mother tongue has an influence in their English language learning.

The result simply implies that mother tongue can greatly affect the learning in English language among senior high school students of Sulu National High School.

In a study conducted by Ochagu, Kaka, and Obim in Nigeria (2022) showed that users of mother tongue have difficulty in learning English language because mother tongue adversely affect their pronunciation of English vowels, consonants, and consonant clusters, as well as supra – segmental like stress and intonation. In another study by Iqbal (2016), it showed that increased emphasis on mother tongue has been shown to lower language learning's accuracy and efficiency. Abdul (2016) in his study revealed that sentences with faults were affected by the use of mother tongue.

3. On the Significant difference in the extent of the influence of mother tongue in English language learning among senior high school students of Sulu National High School, MBHTE – Sulu when data are grouped according to gender, age, grade level, strand, and parent's educational attainment

There is no significant difference in the extent of the influence of mother tongue in English language learning among senior high school students of Sulu National High School, MBHTE – Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender, age, grade level, strand, and parent's educational attainment.

The result implies that mother tongue has no influence in English language learning in terms of gender, age, grade level, strand, and parent's educational attainment.

The study is in agreement to The Contrastive Analysis Hypothesis which was influenced by behaviorist viewpoints. It was anticipated that that interference (or negative transfer) from the first language to the second language may account for almost all errors.

Conclusions

The following was concluded based on the findings of the study:

The senior high school students of Sulu National High School are dominated by male Students, attended school as prescribed by DepEd, and with most parents who did not finish even high school.

It only showed that mother tongue does have an influence on the English language learning among senior high school students of Sulu National High School.

The absence of difference in the extent of the influence of mother tongue in English language learning among senior high school students of Sulu National High School when data are grouped according to gender, age, grade level, strand, parent's educational attainment clearly proves that regardless of the aforementioned profile, the students experienced the same degree of influence in using mother tongue.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

1. Further study on the extent of the influence of mother tongue in English language learning among learners must be conducted to really discover the degree of its influence on them.
2. Future researchers on the same topic should add variables like teaching methods and strategies used by English teachers in teaching the subject.
3. English teachers should constantly encourage learners to speak English in school and practice speaking the language with classmates and peers.
4. English teachers should give their best in teaching the English language and should refrain from code – switching in teaching the language.
5. Teachers should only use mother tongue for emphasis purposes and not entirely during lectures in English class.

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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The ethical consideration of all research participants is paramount, particularly that of the Sulu National High School faculty. The researcher consistently upheld respondents' right to privacy while doing important study.

First and foremost, each participant was provided with a comprehensive informed consent form that detailed the goals of the study, its methods, potential advantages and risks, and its confidentiality policies. Furthermore, each trial data point was painstakingly anonymised in cases where the respondents' personal information had no bearing on the trial results. Data collection was conducted in a private environment to preserve participant privacy, and the collected data was kept in a secure archive that was only accessible by the researchers. In a same spirit, each member was respected despite having different beliefs and points of view. In addition, the researchers made an effort to provide a secure and welcoming environment for the participants so they could openly talk about their experiences.

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